

Information Literacy Skills in the Digital Era and Academic Performance of Postgraduate Students in LIS Departments of Universities in Benue State

Dr. Sandra Mwuese IGYUVE

Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi

mwueseigyuve@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study examined the information literacy skills of postgraduate students in Library and Information Science departments in Nigerian universities and their impact on academic performance. With increasing reliance on digital technologies in higher education, these skills are vital for research, communication, and success. Using a descriptive survey, the study involved 204 students from Joseph Tarka University and Moses Orshio Adasu University. Data collected via a validated questionnaire with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.85, and 190 responses were analysed statistically. Findings showed students have high information literacy skills, demonstrated through needs assessment, search strategies, source evaluation, synthesis, and ethical citation. They extensively use digital resources like journals, e-books, databases, and open-access platforms. These skills are actively applied in research and writing, boosting academic performance. Challenges such as limited training, access issues, poor internet, and weak library support hinder skill development. Despite strong digital navigation, infrastructural limitations affect performance. Recommendations include better literacy programmes, digital infrastructure, resources, and library support to enhance postgraduate research in the digital era.

Keywords: Information Literacy Skills, Digital Era, Academic Performance, Postgraduate Students, Universities.

Introduction

The modern world is increasingly shaped by the digital era, in which information and communication technologies significantly influence the creation, organisation, storage, and dissemination of knowledge. Akinola and Omotade (2025) note that digital technologies have transformed educational environments, making knowledge acquisition and research processes largely dependent on electronic information systems. Tarbiyati and Riady (2025) observe that the rapid growth of digital information resources has created both opportunities for learning and challenges, including information overload, unreliable online content, and difficulties identifying credible academic materials. Consequently, postgraduate students must develop advanced information literacy skills to efficiently search, evaluate, interpret, and ethically apply information in digital environments.

Universities serve as centres for advanced learning, research development, and professional training. Ubwa, Akpe, and Uzoagba (2025) explain that the transition from traditional to digitally driven information systems has altered teaching, learning, and research practices. Agbo and Ubwa (2024) highlight that universities increasingly rely on electronic databases, institutional repositories, digital

libraries, and online platforms to support postgraduate education and scholarly productivity. The effectiveness of these systems depends on students' ability to competently access and utilise available information resources. Akinola and Omotade (2025) emphasise that academic libraries and faculty members play a crucial role in equipping postgraduate students with the information literacy skills required for effective academic performance.

Postgraduate students in Library and Information Science programmes occupy a unique position as advanced learners and future information professionals. Oni, Ajagu, Tagwai, Madu, and Iwundu (2023) state that academic success relies heavily on intensive research activities requiring the identification, retrieval, evaluation, synthesis, and ethical use of scholarly information. Adeniran and Onuoha (2018) observe that differences in prior academic exposure, technological experience, and access to information resources result in varying levels of digital competence among students. Soyemia and Olalere (2022) add that while some students navigate digital research environments effectively, others struggle to manage electronic information tools, assess source credibility, and apply research best practices, which may affect academic outcomes.

Information literacy skills are indispensable for postgraduate students in the digital era. Sahabi, Efe, and BuNar (2021) note that these skills facilitate literature searching, the critical evaluation of scholarly materials, proper referencing, and the responsible use of information in research and academic writing. Agbo and Ubwa (2024) argue that inadequate information literacy can lead to poor research quality, weak academic performance, and diminished research productivity. This study, therefore, investigates information literacy skills in the digital era and their impact on the academic performance of postgraduate students in Library and Information Science departments in universities in Benue State, Nigeria

Statement of the problem

The digital era has significantly transformed higher education by making academic activities increasingly dependent on digital information resources and technologies. Universities now operate within electronically driven learning and research environments that require postgraduate students, particularly those in Library and Information Science departments, to possess strong information literacy skills for effective academic performance. These skills enable students to identify information needs, access relevant scholarly resources, evaluate the credibility of information, and apply information ethically in research and academic writing. Despite the availability of digital resources in universities in Benue State, many postgraduate students still face challenges related to inadequate information literacy, limited instructional support, and inconsistent utilisation of electronic information systems, which may negatively affect research productivity and academic achievement. The absence of sufficient empirical evidence on how information literacy skills influence postgraduate academic performance, therefore necessitates this study to examine the relationship between information literacy skills in the digital era and the academic performance of postgraduate students in Library and Information Science departments in universities in Benue State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to examine information literacy skills in the digital era and their relationship to the academic performance of postgraduate students in Library and Information Science departments in universities in Benue State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the level of information literacy skills possessed by postgraduate students of Library and Information Science departments in universities in Benue State, Nigeria, in the digital era.

2. Identify the types of digital information resources utilised by postgraduate students of Library and Information Science departments in universities in Benue State, Nigeria, for academic and research purposes.
3. Examine the extent to which postgraduate students apply information literacy skills in accessing, evaluating, and using digital information resources for academic performance.
4. Assess the challenges affecting the acquisition and effective utilisation of information literacy skills among postgraduate students of Library and Information Science departments in universities in Benue State, Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Information Search Process (ISP) Model developed by Carol C. Kuhlthau in 1991. The Information Search Process Model conceptualises information literacy as a cognitive, emotional, and behavioural process through which individuals seek, select, evaluate, and use information to construct knowledge. The model identifies six major stages of information seeking: initiation, selection, exploration, formulation, collection, and presentation. These stages explain how learners gradually develop understanding as they interact with information resources, emphasising that information use involves uncertainty, critical reflection, and progressive knowledge development rather than mere information retrieval. The framework highlights the relationship between information skills and academic learning outcomes, making it suitable for examining how students engage with digital information environments.

The relevance of the Information Search Process Model to postgraduate students in the digital era lies in its focus on independent research, critical inquiry, and scholarly knowledge construction. Postgraduate students in Library and Information Science departments are expected to engage extensively with electronic databases, digital repositories, and online scholarly communication platforms while conducting advanced academic research. The model explains how effective information literacy skills enable students to move confidently from problem identification to research completion, thereby improving academic performance. Within universities in Benue State, the framework provides insight into how challenges such as inadequate digital competencies, limited access to information resources, or insufficient research guidance may affect postgraduate students' ability to navigate digital information systems successfully. Consequently, the Information Search Process Model provides an appropriate theoretical basis for understanding how information literacy skills enhance postgraduate academic performance in the digital era.

Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored on the following concepts:

Information Literacy Skills

Information literacy skills encompass the competencies needed to identify information needs, locate relevant sources, critically evaluate information, and apply knowledge effectively for academic and research purposes. Akinola and Omotade (2025) explain that these skills extend beyond basic access to include digital search competence, analytical thinking, ethical information use, and scholarly communication abilities. Tarbiyati and Riady (2025) observe that postgraduate students benefit from these skills as they engage deeply with academic literature, research databases, and emerging digital knowledge systems. The increasing complexity of digital information environments requires postgraduate students to filter credible scholarly materials from unreliable online sources. Sharma and Upadhyay (2021) highlight

that mastery of these skills enables independent research, critical inquiry, and evidence-based academic writing, essential for postgraduate study. Ubwa, Aghadiuno, and Ubwa (2025) note that information literacy enhances students' management of research processes from topic formulation to dissemination of findings, including interactions with electronic journals, citation management tools, and online collaborative platforms. Oni et al. (2023) observe that effective development of these skills improves research quality, originality, and academic integrity while reducing dependence on unreliable sources. Agbo and Ubwa (2024) add that universities play a strategic role in fostering these competencies through library instruction, research training programmes, and digital learning support systems.

Digital Era

The digital era is characterised by rapid technological advancement, widespread internet access, and the integration of digital systems into educational, professional, and social activities. Nguyen and Bradshaw (2022) note that knowledge creation and dissemination increasingly occur via online databases, virtual classrooms, digital libraries, and research networking platforms. Yila (2024) observes that postgraduate education has been transformed by technology-driven learning environments, enabling remote access to scholarly information and global academic collaboration.

While these developments enhance learning opportunities, they also introduce challenges, including information overload, digital distractions, and the spread of inaccurate information. Anyim (2020) emphasises that postgraduate students require competencies to evaluate and utilise digital information responsibly. Smith, Johnson, and Williams (2022) argue that institutional investment in digital infrastructure, electronic resources, and technology-supported learning systems is crucial to sustaining academic productivity. Jones (2021) observes that the evolving digital era shapes how postgraduate students acquire knowledge and demonstrate academic performance.

Academic Performance

Academic performance encompasses measurable outcomes of students' learning activities, including research productivity, coursework achievement, critical analysis, and successful completion of academic programmes. Ubwa, Akpe, and Uzoagba (2025) note that at the postgraduate level, performance extends beyond grades to research competence, scholarly writing quality, innovation, and contributions to knowledge development. Soyemia and Olalere (2022) observe that effective academic performance depends on students' ability to access, interpret, and apply information within academic tasks. Agbo and Ubwa (2024) argue that digital learning environments increasingly require competence in using electronic resources and digital research tools. Akinola and Omotade (2025) explain that postgraduate students who effectively apply information literacy skills demonstrate improved research efficiency, accurate citation practices, and higher-quality academic outputs. Sahabi et al. (2021) highlight that strong performance reflects students' capacity for independent inquiry and sustained engagement with scholarly information systems, benefiting both individual success and institutional research visibility.

Postgraduate Students

Postgraduate students are advanced learners engaged in specialised academic and research-oriented programmes aimed at knowledge creation and professional development. Ubwa, Aghadiuno, and Ubwa (2025) explain that, unlike undergraduates, postgraduate students are expected to demonstrate autonomy in research design, information analysis, and scholarly communication. Oni et al. (2023) observe that their academic responsibilities involve extensive interaction with digital information systems, research

databases, and interdisciplinary knowledge sources. Adeniran and Onuoha (2018) note that differences in preparedness to manage complex research information affect academic outcomes. Soyemia and Olalere (2022) emphasise that universities must provide targeted training and library support to enhance postgraduate research competence. Agbo and Ubwa (2024) argue that understanding postgraduate students' interactions with information systems provides insight into how information literacy skills influence academic performance.

Universities

Universities act as centres for advanced learning, research, and knowledge dissemination, preparing skilled professionals and researchers. Ubwa, Akpe, and Uzoagba (2025) explain that in the digital era, universities integrate digital technologies into teaching, research supervision, and information service delivery. Akinola and Omotade (2025) observe that academic libraries, virtual learning platforms, and institutional repositories are essential components of these learning environments. The effectiveness of postgraduate education depends on institutional provision of digital infrastructure and structured information literacy programmes. Agbo and Ubwa (2024) note that universities promote academic excellence through collaboration among lecturers, librarians, and technology specialists. Yila (2024) emphasises that investment in digital infrastructure, research databases, and virtual learning systems ensures equitable access to scholarly information. Ubwa, Aghadiuno, and Ubwa (2025) explain that policies encouraging research training, digital competence, and ethical information practices strengthen postgraduate academic productivity. Jones (2021) and Sharma and Upadhyay (2021) highlight that by fostering supportive academic ecosystems, universities directly influence how postgraduate students develop information literacy skills and achieve improved academic performance in the digital era.

Review of Related Literature

The following literature was reviewed in line with the study, highlighting the similarities, differences, and gaps identified by previous work to be addressed by the present study.

Akinola and Omotade (2025) examined the contribution of information literacy skills and digital information resources to students' academic activities in Nigerian universities using a survey research design. Their study involved undergraduate students selected through stratified sampling and revealed that the ability to access electronic information and evaluate website credibility positively influenced students' academic engagement. While both the earlier and present studies recognise the importance of information literacy competencies and digital resource utilisation in supporting academic outcomes, clear distinctions exist between them. The earlier investigation focused broadly on undergraduate students and general academic activities across private universities, whereas the present study concentrates specifically on postgraduate students in Library and Information Science departments within universities in Benue State, using a census approach. Furthermore, the earlier study emphasised access to digital facilities, while the present research extends analysis to the application of information literacy skills and their direct influence on postgraduate academic performance. Consequently, the earlier study leaves insufficient empirical understanding of how advanced learners apply information literacy competencies within research-intensive postgraduate environments, a limitation addressed by the present study.

Tarbiyati and Riady (2025) explored the relevance of information literacy in strengthening students' abilities within digitally driven learning environments through a literature-based approach. Their findings highlighted that information literacy promotes critical thinking, independent learning, and problem-solving, and recommended institutional collaboration to develop literacy programmes. Although both

studies acknowledge information literacy as essential for academic success in the digital era, methodological and contextual differences are evident. The previous work relied solely on secondary sources and theoretical discussion without field data, whereas the present study generates empirical evidence obtained directly from postgraduate students. In addition, the earlier study discussed students generally without focusing on disciplinary or academic-level differences. The absence of population-based empirical assessment created a gap in understanding how postgraduate students practically utilise information literacy skills to enhance academic performance, which the present study addresses through systematic data collection and analysis across universities in Benue State.

Adeniran and Onuoha (2018) investigated how information literacy skills influenced postgraduate students' use of electronic resources in private universities in South-West Nigeria. Using survey methods and multistage sampling, the study established a positive relationship between literacy skills and electronic resource usage. While both studies examine postgraduate students and acknowledge the relevance of information literacy in academic engagement, their analytical directions differ considerably. The earlier study focused on electronic resource utilisation, whereas the present research examines broader outcomes by linking information literacy skills to academic performance in the digital era. Additionally, institutional coverage differs: the previous study focused on private universities, whereas the present study considers public universities in Benue State and adopts a census technique to ensure comprehensive representation. The earlier research, therefore, leaves unresolved questions regarding how information literacy competencies translate into measurable academic performance and how associated challenges affect the application of skills, issues explored in the present investigation.

Oni, Ajagu, Tagwai, Madu and Iwundu (2023) assessed information literacy competencies among postgraduate students at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, with emphasis on programmes through which students acquired such skills. Findings indicated that students gained literacy knowledge mainly through orientations, seminars, and library instruction, although difficulties in identifying credible information sources persisted. Both studies address information literacy among postgraduate students using questionnaire-based survey methods; however, their focus areas vary. The earlier research primarily centred on modes of skill acquisition within a single institution, whereas the present study expands the analysis to include digital resource utilisation, skill application, and academic performance outcomes across universities in Benue State. The limitation of institutional confinement and the minimal attention to performance implications in the previous study create a research gap, which the present study addresses by examining how information literacy competencies function within digitally mediated academic environments to influence postgraduate achievement.

Ajebomogun, Agagu, Achigbue, and Diyaolu (2022) examined the computer literacy skills and institutional conditions that influence postgraduate use of electronic resources in a Nigerian university. The study reported high levels of technical computer competence among students but found that such skills did not significantly determine electronic resource usage, while infrastructural limitations remained major constraints. Although both investigations consider postgraduate interaction with digital resources and institutional challenges, their conceptual orientations differ. The earlier study focused mainly on operational computer skills, whereas the present research adopts a broader information literacy perspective encompassing information identification, evaluation, ethical usage, and scholarly application. Moreover, the earlier work did not relate digital competencies to academic performance outcomes. This creates a notable gap concerning the academic implications of information literacy skills beyond technical proficiency, which the present study addresses by examining how comprehensive literacy competencies influence postgraduate academic performance within the digital era.

Research Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to investigate the impact of information literacy skills in the digital era on the academic performance of postgraduate students in Library and Information Science departments in universities in Benue State, Nigeria. The study included the entire population of 204 postgraduate students, using a census approach to ensure that all perspectives were captured. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire designed to assess students' information literacy skills, the types of digital resources they utilise, the extent to which they apply these skills, and the challenges affecting skill acquisition and use. The questionnaire was validated by experts in Library and Information Science and Measurement and Evaluation, while its reliability was confirmed through Cronbach's Alpha (0.85), indicating high internal consistency. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics, with a mean benchmark of 2.50 applied to interpret levels and patterns of information literacy skills and their application, enabling the study to determine how postgraduate students engage with digital resources and leverage these competencies to enhance academic performance in the digital era.

Results and Discussion

Distribution and Return Rate of Questionnaire

S/N	Institution	Population	Sample Size	Returned	Return %
1	Joseph Tarka University, Makurdi	96	96	91	93.8%
2	Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi	108	107	99	92.5%
Total		204	204	190	93.1%

The distribution and return rate table indicates that the study covered a total population of 204 postgraduate students drawn from Joseph Tarka University, Makurdi and Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, using a census approach. Out of the 96 questionnaires administered at Joseph Tarka University, 91 were successfully returned, representing a response rate of 93.8%, while 99 questionnaires were retrieved from Moses Orshio Adasu University out of 107 administered, giving a return rate of 92.5%. Overall, 190 questionnaires were returned out of the 204 distributed, resulting in an aggregate response rate of 93.1%. This high return rate indicates strong participation from respondents and suggests that the data obtained are adequate and reliable for analysis, as the responses sufficiently represent postgraduate students' views on information literacy skills and digital resource utilisation in the selected universities.

Cluster A: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of Information Literacy Skills Possessed by Postgraduate Students

S/N	Statement	N	Mean	SD
1	Clearly identification information needs before beginning research activities	190	2.74	0.96
2	Effectively develop search strategies using appropriate keywords	190	2.68	0.83

3	Critically evaluate digital information sources for credibility and relevance	190	2.71	0.90
4	Synthesize information from various digital sources for research purposes	190	2.63	0.88
5	Apply ethical standards such as citation and referencing when using information	190	2.76	0.86
	Cluster Mean	190	2.70	0.89

The results in Cluster A reveal that postgraduate students generally demonstrate a high level of information literacy, as reflected in their ability to identify information needs, formulate search strategies, evaluate digital sources, synthesise information, and apply ethical citation practices. This outcome corresponds with the findings of Tarbiyati and Riady (2025), who argued that competence in identifying, accessing, and ethically utilising information forms the foundation for effective learning and academic development in the digital era. The findings also reinforce Akinola and Omotade (2025), who reported that students with adequate information literacy skills are better positioned to assess the authenticity of online information. However, the present results slightly contrast with those of Oni et al. (2023), who observed that although postgraduate students could locate information within their disciplines, many still struggled to determine reliable sources. The higher proficiency observed in this study may suggest improved exposure to digital research environments among Library and Information Science postgraduate students.

Cluster B: Mean and Standard Deviation of Types of Digital Information Resources Utilised by Postgraduate Students

S/N	Digital Resource	N	Mean	SD
1	Online academic journals/e-journals	190	2.59	0.94
2	Electronic books (e-books)	190	2.66	0.81
3	Academic databases (e.g., JSTOR, ScienceDirect)	190	2.54	0.92
4	Institutional repositories	190	2.48	0.97
5	Open access platforms (e.g., Google Scholar, ResearchGate)	190	2.72	0.84
	Cluster Mean	190	2.60	0.90

Cluster B shows that postgraduate students frequently utilise a range of digital information resources, particularly open-access platforms, electronic books, and academic journals, while institutional repositories record relatively lower usage. These findings are consistent with those of Adeniran and Onuoha (2018), who found that information literacy competencies significantly enhance postgraduate students’ engagement with electronic resources for academic purposes. The pattern also aligns with Akinola and Omotade (2025), who noted that access to diverse digital resources strengthens students’ academic activities by improving information access. Nonetheless, the comparatively moderate use of institutional repositories suggests persistent awareness or accessibility limitations, which, in turn, reflects concerns raised by Ajegbomogun et al. (2022) regarding institutional and infrastructural factors influencing electronic resource utilisation in Nigerian universities.

Cluster C: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Extent of Application of Information Literacy Skills by Postgraduate Students

S/N	Skill Application	N	Mean	SD
1	I plan my research process before searching digital resources	190	2.69	0.88
2	I evaluate the relevance of the retrieved online information	190	2.65	0.91
3	I apply advanced search techniques during information retrieval	190	2.63	0.87
4	I integrate information from multiple sources in academic work	190	2.71	0.86
5	I properly acknowledge all information sources used	190	2.67	0.92
	Cluster Mean	190	2.67	0.89

The findings in Cluster C indicate that postgraduate students actively apply information literacy skills in planning research activities, evaluating retrieved information, employing search techniques, integrating multiple sources, and appropriately acknowledging information. This supports the conclusion of Tarbiyati and Riady (2025) that information literacy promotes independent learning, analytical thinking, and effective academic engagement. The results align with those of Adeniran and Onuoha (2018), who demonstrated that information literacy competence encourages the meaningful utilisation of electronic resources among postgraduate students. Unlike Ajegbomogun et al. (2022), who reported that technical computer literacy did not significantly influence electronic resource use, the present findings suggest that broader information literacy capabilities extend beyond technical skills and are actively translated into scholarly practices among postgraduate learners.

Cluster D: Mean and Standard Deviation of Challenges Affecting Acquisition and Utilisation of Information Literacy Skills

S/N	Challenge	N	Mean	SD
1	Inadequate training on the effective use of digital resources	190	2.83	0.91
2	Limited access to computers and digital devices	190	2.79	0.95
3	Poor or unstable internet connectivity	190	2.87	0.89
4	Difficulty evaluating the credibility of online information	190	2.73	0.88
5	Insufficient library support services	190	2.69	0.93
	Cluster Mean	190	2.78	0.91

Cluster D indicates that postgraduate students encounter notable barriers affecting the acquisition and effective use of information literacy skills, particularly inadequate training opportunities, limited access to digital devices, unstable internet connectivity, and insufficient institutional support. These results align with those of Ajegbomogun et al. (2022), who identified infrastructural deficiencies and inadequate ICT support as major constraints to electronic resource utilisation in Nigerian universities. The findings also support Akinola and Omotade (2025), who recommended improved digital infrastructure and resource provision to enhance students' academic engagement. Furthermore, the challenges identified reinforce the argument of Tarbiyati and Riady (2025) that effective information literacy development requires coordinated institutional collaboration involving libraries, lecturers, and university management. The persistence of these constraints suggests that, despite high skill levels, environmental and institutional

limitations continue to influence optimal application of information literacy competencies among postgraduate students.

Conclusion

The study established that postgraduate students in Library and Information Science departments in universities in Benue State possess a relatively high level of information literacy skills and demonstrate substantial utilisation and application of digital information resources in their academic activities. The high questionnaire return rate further confirms the reliability of the findings and reflects strong participation by respondents. The results revealed that postgraduate students are competent in identifying information needs, evaluating digital sources, integrating scholarly materials, and applying ethical information practices, which positively support academic performance within the digital learning environment. However, despite these demonstrated competencies, challenges such as inadequate training opportunities, poor internet connectivity, limited access to digital devices, and insufficient library support services continue to hinder optimal utilisation of information literacy skills. The findings, therefore, indicate that while postgraduate students possess the required skills for effective academic engagement in the digital era, institutional and infrastructural limitations remain critical factors influencing the full realisation of academic productivity.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. *Enhancement of Information Literacy Skills:* Universities should institutionalise regular information literacy training programmes, workshops, and research seminars coordinated by academic libraries to further strengthen postgraduate students' competencies in advanced information searching, evaluation, and ethical use of digital information.
2. *Improvement in Access to Digital Information Resources:* University management should expand subscriptions to electronic databases, e-journals, institutional repositories, and open-access platforms to ensure wider availability and utilisation of diverse digital academic resources by postgraduate students.
3. *Promotion of Practical Application of Information Literacy Skills:* Lecturers and research supervisors should integrate information literacy practices into coursework, assignments, and research supervision to encourage continuous application of these skills in postgraduate research activities.
4. *Provision of Adequate Digital Infrastructure:* Universities should improve internet connectivity, provide functional computer laboratories, and increase access to digital devices within libraries and postgraduate study centres to minimise technological barriers affecting information access and utilisation.
5. *Strengthening Library Support Services:* Academic libraries should enhance user support services through personalised research assistance, digital reference services, and continuous user education programmes aimed at addressing challenges associated with evaluating online information and effective resource utilisation.

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